

Impact Study

Biofuel

Production

Biofuel production

Context

[Transportation is responsible for nearly a quarter](#) of global greenhouse gas emissions and remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels: meeting climate targets will require a mix of technologies working together towards a more sustainable future. While electrification offers a [path forward for some vehicles](#), transport biofuels, renewable alternatives made from plant biomass and agricultural waste, are a key component of this transition. They are especially important for heavy-duty trucks, aviation, and maritime transport, where energy density and infrastructure limitations [make electrification less feasible](#). As of 2022, biofuels represented nearly 90% of the renewable energy consumed for transport, with a mix of emerging and production-level technologies driving continued progress.

This case study demonstrates how biodata resources are contributing to the development of biofuels, from those produced from traditional agricultural waste to innovative ways to leverage previously unknown micro-organisms.

Improving the efficiency of biofuel production

In 2025, researchers at the Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM), in collaboration with international partners, [identified CelOCE](#) (cellulose oxidative cleaving enzyme), a natural enzyme that promotes cellulose breakdown into soluble sugars, with applications in the production of renewable fuels and biochemicals.

Researchers discovered that combining CelOCE with other enzymes doubles the efficiency of cellulose breakdown compared to previous methods, representing a significant shift in methods used for biomass conversion. This discovery [enables increased production of second-generation ethanol](#), a clean fuel produced from agricultural waste like sugarcane bagasse and corn straw.

CelOCE's industrial applicability has been demonstrated at pilot scale, and a patent application has been filed for its use in biomass conversion and related biotechnological applications. Brazil, as a major producer of biofuels, operates the only two commercial biorefineries in the world capable of producing biofuels from cellulose at scale. The integration of CelOCE into these facilities is expected to significantly enhance the efficiency of these facilities, with potential for replication in other countries.

The discovery and characterisation of CelOCE were made possible by open biodata resources, including the [NCBI RefSeq database](#) and the [Protein Data Bank \(PDB\)](#). Researchers mined the previously unclassified DNA of a microbial community specialised in lignocellulose degradation, and were able to identify genes with unique signatures linked to cellulose degradation. These genes were then synthesised, tested and structurally characterised with the help of biodata resources, prior to demonstrations in pilot plant bioreactors.

Learning from nature

In 2024, researchers from RIKEN in Japan [discovered a microbe](#) called Met12 in the Californian wilderness. Met12 belongs to a group of anaerobic microbes typically associated with methane production, yet it does not possess the genes required for this. Instead, through a unique gene called MmcX, it can turn carbon dioxide into acetate through electron transfer.

The study outlining the discovery of MmcX highlights the use of biodata resources in significant detail, showing the depth and breadth of these digital infrastructures. Key databases involved in this work included [NCBI Sequence Read Archive](#), [NCBI GenBank](#), the [Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes \(KEGG\)](#) and [Archaeal Clusters of Orthologous Groups \(arCOGs\)](#). These were complemented by the use of bioinformatics resources, such as [GhostKOALA](#), [SignalP](#), [GTDB-Tk](#) (which in turn relies on the [Genome Taxonomy Database](#)), [ColabFold](#) (based on AlphaFold2) and more.

Once characterised, the MmcX gene was inserted into a bacterium and was shown to facilitate energy metabolism with carbon dioxide as the primary fuel source. This enhanced bacterium is commonly used to make chemicals and biofuels, which led the research team to [file a patent](#) for the new molecular technology. Importantly, there is also recognition that the discovery could aid in carbon sequestration — another priority activity for slowing the pace of climate change.

The discovery is also guiding the search for new microbes in other extreme environments, such as hot springs in Japan and deep-sea volcanoes, which might unlock further innovation through bio-inspired applications.

Conclusions

These examples show how open biodata and bioinformatics resources are transforming fundamental research into practical solutions for clean energy. By providing unrestricted access to data — along with advanced computational tools — they enable faster discovery, modelling and optimisation of biological systems for industrial applications.

Such capabilities are already delivering tangible results: improving the efficiency of biofuel production, enabling new pathways for carbon capture and laying the groundwork for cleaner technologies in line with global climate goals.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
arCOGs Database	The archaeal clusters of orthologous groups (arCOGs) Database is a curated database of clusters of genes within the archaeal domain with shared evolutionary history that can be used for the functional annotation of archaeal genomes.
ColabFold	ColabFold supports protein structure and complex prediction, generating sequence alignments and templates. The tool uses AlphaFold2 and AlphaFold2-multimer to make protein folding accessible to all. The accelerated prediction enables nearly 1,000 structure predictions a day on a server having only one graphics processing unit, removing the need for local high computational requirements.
GenBank	GenBank is the NIH's comprehensive genetic sequence database. GenBank provides an annotated collection of all publicly available DNA sequences. As part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, GenBank shares data with other organisations on a daily basis to provide access for the scientific community to the most comprehensive and up-to-date DNA sequence information.

Resources	About
<u>Genome Taxonomy Database</u>	<p>The Genome Taxonomy Database provides a standardised microbial taxonomy based on genome phylogeny, covering both bacteria and archaea. Alongside genomes drawn from resources such as RefSeq and GenBank, the resource includes 'draft genomes of uncultured microorganisms obtained from metagenomes and single cells' which improves microbial world genomic representation.</p>
<u>GhostKOALA</u>	<p>GhostKOALA (KEGG Orthology And Links Annotation) is a web-based tool for the automatic annotation of genome and metagenome sequences, developed by the KEGG team. Users upload amino acid sequence data, which is compared against the KEGG GENES database (a collection of genes and proteins) to assign functional annotations. The tool can process datasets containing up to 500,000 sequences.</p>
<u>GTDB-Tk</u>	<p>GTDB-Tk (Genome Taxonomy Database Toolkit) is a software toolkit for assigning taxonomic classifications to bacterial and archaeal genomes. It uses phylogenetic placement methods to compare genomes against a reference tree and determine their taxonomy from domain to species level. The tool is used for classifying newly sequenced genomes and metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs).</p>
<u>KEGG PATHWAY Database</u>	<p>The KEGG PATHWAY Database ((Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes) is a collection of manually created biological pathway maps that represent molecular interaction, reaction and relation networks. Kanehisa Laboratories has been developing the KEGG database as a computer model of biological systems.</p>
<u>Worldwide Protein Data Bank</u>	<p>The Worldwide Protein Data Bank (PDB) provides access to 3D structure data for the molecules of life, such as RNA, DNA and proteins, that are found in all organisms on the planet. The PDB was established as the first open access digital data resource in all of biology and medicine. It is now a leading global resource for experimental data central to scientific discovery.</p>

Resources	About
RefSeq	<p>The Reference Sequence (RefSeq) is a collection of annotated sequences provided by the National Library of Medicine. The collection covers genomic DNA, proteins and transcripts, and forms a foundation for functional, medical and diversity studies. This resource provides a reference for genome annotation, gene identification and mutation analysis. Bacteria, archaea and viruses are included in the database.</p>
Sequence Re Archive	<p>The SRA is the largest publicly available repository that contains high throughput sequencing data, including all branches of life, together with metagenomic and environmental surveys. Included in the SRA is raw sequencing data and alignment information, which supports new discoveries through data analysis. Data relates to clinically important studies involving human subjects or their metagenomes.</p>
SignalP	<p>SignalP is a web-based tool that predicts whether proteins contain signal peptides (short sequences that direct proteins to be secreted or transported to specific cellular locations) and identifies where these signal peptides are cleaved. The tool works across all domains of life (Archaea, Bacteria, and Eukarya) and can distinguish between different types of signal peptides in prokaryotes. Users can submit up to 1,000 protein sequences for analysis.</p>

Global Biodata Coalition

🌐 www.globalbiodata.org

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